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Calibration of Star Mapper distortion

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It may be feasible to determine the large-scale distortion of the Star Mapper grid from data conveniently gathered in the course of the normal Attitude Reconstitution. The principle would be to accumulate, simultaneously with the AR processing of SM transits, the normal equations for the corrections to certain coefficients of the polynomials for the SM centre lines. The corrections are regarded as fully decoupled from the attitude parameters, and no cross-matrix is therefore computed. The only reason for doing the accumulation on-line, rather than in an a posteriori analysis of residuals, is that the necessary data happen to be around.

If the SM slits are intended to be straight in the (w,z) plane (a projection normal to the tangent plane through the grid centre), it may be sufficient to represent the centre lines by the functions

$$w = fh + w_{10} + w_{11}z + w_{12}z^2 \quad (\text{vertical group, } g = 1) \quad (1)$$

$$w = fh + w_{20} + \begin{cases} \bar{w}_{21}z + \bar{w}_{22}z^2 & (z > 0) \\ \bar{w}'_{21}z + \bar{w}'_{22}z^2 & (z < 0) \end{cases} \quad (\text{chevron group, } g = 2) \quad (2)$$

where f is the field index. [For the SM grid on the +w side of the primary grid, the nominal parameters are $w_{10} \approx 0.00936$, $w_{20} \approx 0.01543$, $-\bar{w}_{21} = \bar{w}'_{21} = 1$, $h = w_{11} = w_{12} = \bar{w}_{22} = \bar{w}'_{22} = 0$.]

Although the origin of w is determined by the primary grid, it is still necessary to adopt a fixed value for w_{10} (the position of the vertical group centre) in order to determine the spin phase angle Ω of the attitude. The correction to this assumed w_{10} will actually appear in the attitude solution of the set solutions (Ω_k). It appears possible, however, to determine all remaining eight parameters in (1)-(2) from the transit time residuals, if required.

If all eight parameters are to be calibrated (which may not be necessary), the main part of the process would be to calculate and accumulate 44 numbers for each SM transit, probably using exclusively field coordinates etc which are already available at that moment.